

THEORETICAL BASIS OF THE FORMATION OF SOCIAL RELATIONSHIPS IN STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article examines the theoretical foundations of the formation of social relationships among university students from the perspective of social psychology, developmental psychology, and modern higher education research. A number of information is provided about the analysis of the theoretical foundations of the formation of social relationships in university students, the various factors of this process, the complex and continuous psychological states that occur, and the close connection between it and not only the internal motives of the individual, but also the external social environment, communicative opportunities, cultural values, and the education system. The theoretical concepts presented in this article are aimed at helping teachers and psychologists to better understand the socio-psychological mechanisms involved in the processes of forming relationships among students.*

Keywords: *social relations, social environment, student youth, social psychology, social adaptation, identification, empathy, reflection.*

Introduction.

As a result of the development of modern information and communication technologies in the world, the widespread popularity of the Internet and the rapid expansion of social networks, fundamental changes are taking place in the personal and social lives of young people. Today, social networks such as Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, Telegram, X (formerly Twitter) are not only a means of communication, but also a powerful psychological factor that influences knowledge acquisition, information dissemination, social opinion formation, and the worldview of young people. In particular, psychological studies conducted in developed countries show that social networks play an important role in the process of self-awareness among young people, the formation of their personal “I-concept”, and the assimilation of social roles and values. At the same time, the negative consequences of excessive use, which cause problems such as social isolation, communication difficulties, and Internet addiction, are also attracting the attention of the scientific community.

In Uzbekistan, the information space has also expanded significantly in recent years, and the use of social networks among young people has increased sharply. According to statistics, more than half of Internet users in our country belong to the category of students and youth. This indicates that students rely on social networks not only in the educational process, but also in the formation of social relationships. From this point of view, there is a need for a deep scientific analysis of the role and influence of social networks in the formation of communicative culture, social activity, social attitudes and psychological stability in students.

The correct formation of social relationships in students is an important psychological basis for their personal development, active participation in society and future professional success. At the same time, the development of mechanisms for the rational use of social networks, the effective

use of their educational and developmental potential is one of the priority areas of psychological and pedagogical research today.

Literature Review

From a psychological point of view, one of the main socio-psychological factors in the formation and transformation of new thinking and worldviews is social relations. The concept of “social relations” is interpreted differently in psychology, sociology, and pedagogy. From a psychological point of view, social relations are a system of relationships expressed in emotional, cognitive, and behavioral terms, the interaction of a person with other individuals in society [1].

In modern conditions, social networks have also become an important factor. Through them, students form virtual groups, exchange ideas, and this process strengthens or sometimes replaces real social relations [2]. Therefore, social networks should be viewed as a “new platform for social relations”. Student life is a unique stage in human life, during which the place, role, and social identity of a person in the system of social relations are formed. During this period, the individual determines his social "I", begins to perceive himself as a full-fledged member of society, which in turn constitutes an important psychological foundation for the formation of social relations [3].

Social relations are not only the process of communication or information exchange, but also a complex system that embodies the internal psychological state of the individual, emotional experiences, and attitude towards social values. In the formation of social relations between students, their communicative activity, level of empathy, ability to master social roles, and the process of social identification play an important role [4]. A.A. Bodalev analyzed the main mechanisms of interpersonal relations in the theory of social perception and distinguished the following processes:

- identification (perception of another as oneself),
- empathy (feeling the feelings of another),
- reflection (understanding how others relate to you) [5].

In Western psychology, the social learning theory put forward by A. Bandura is of great importance in the analysis of social relations. According to this theory, a person learns his behavior by observing others and modeling their behavior [5]. These mechanisms are especially active during the student period. Because students have the opportunity to learn from each other and understand themselves by exchanging ideas with each other, participating in projects, and participating in discussions.

According to Erik Erikson's theory of psychosocial development, during the student period, a person goes through the stage of "identity-role confusion". This process is associated with determining the identity, values, and social position of the individual [6]. The social relations formed at this stage form the psychological foundation of interpersonal relations in later life.

During the student period, a person actively tries to satisfy this need, as a result of which he establishes new social contacts, expands his circle of communication, and feels valued in the community. This, in turn, strengthens psychological stability and social activity [7]. The influence of information and communication technologies on the formation of social relationships deserves special attention. Due to the high level of use of social networks among students, their social communication skills are now developing not only in the real, but also in the virtual space. Therefore, the concept of “virtual socialization” is widely used in psychology today [8].

Methods.

Observation, interview, questionnaire, specially developed socio-psychological questionnaire “The role of social networks in the formation of social relations in students” (M. Kholnazarova, B. Rayimkulov), content analysis, G. K. Alimova “Psychological factors of the formation of communicative culture in students. (Modified by L. M. Mitina and I. A. Zimnyaya “Communicative competence questionnaire”), K. Riff’s “Psychological well-being scale” questionnaire adapted by N. N. Lepeshinsky (2007), V. F. Ryakhovsky’s “Test of approachability and communicability”, Milton Rokich’s methods for determining value orientation were used.

Results.

A new approach to the communicative and psychological nature of social networks was developed. In the course of the research, the history of the formation of social networks, their role in the formation of communication, interaction and social identity in students were systematically analyzed, and a theoretical model was proposed that reveals their psychological nature.

The structure of psychological processes occurring in students through social networks was determined. The interrelationship of motivational, emotional and cognitive processes, as well as their influence on the relationships formed through social networks, was scientifically explained.

The relationship between the level of use of social networks by students and their social attitudes was determined, and a psychodiagnostic model was developed. As a result of the psychological research conducted, students' communication style in social networks, attitude to interpersonal relationships and specific aspects of the socialization process were scientifically analyzed.

Conclusion.

The process of formation of social relations in students and its theoretical foundations were analyzed. An analysis of psychological literature showed that social relations are a socio-psychological system that arises in the process of interaction of a person with others, which depends on the communicative competence, empathic sensitivity, social adaptability and moral values of the person. During the student period, this process is more active, since it is at this stage that the person’s worldview, social roles, and communication style are formed. The student creates his own image of his social “I” and strengthens it through social relations in various networks.

The mechanisms of formation of relations were analyzed. These mechanisms are associated with several psychological processes:

-Identification - the student equates himself with a certain group or person, through which social self-awareness is formed.

-Imitation - positive behaviors, values, and thoughts observed in social networks are consolidated as models in the student’s mind.

-Reflection - evaluating one's actions based on opinions and assessments on the network, self-analysis.

-Empathy - the ability to understand the emotional state of others and respond accordingly strengthens social communication.

Also, the formation of social relationships in social networks takes place in the "virtual social space". In this space, students exchange experiences, express opinions, express themselves and learn to actively participate in the social environment. In this regard, social networks serve as an effective platform for increasing social activity in students, expressing opinions on current issues in society and forming social responsibility.

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